

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 31 (2020) 155-174

EISSN 2543-5426

Packed bed column adsorption of oil and grease from refinery desalter effluent, using rice husks derived carbon as the adsorbent: Influence of process parameters and Bohart–Adams kinetics study

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ABSTRACT

Oil and grease (O&G) adsorption in a packed bed column, using adsorbent prepared from rice husks wastes, was investigated. The effects of adsorbent particle size (150, 300, and 600 μm), initial adsorbate concentration (200, 300, and 400 mg/L), and bed height (100, 200, and 300 mm) on the performance of column adsorption for O&G removal and breakthrough time were investigated in the packed column experiments at a constant flow rate of 10.5 mL/min. The kinetic behavior of the column adsorption process was analyzed using the Bohart–Adams model. The kinetic data fitted the model very well. The rate constant (mass transfer coefficient) for Bohart–Adams model (K_{AB}) increased with the decrease in adsorbent particle size and initial ion concentration but was higher at the bed height of 200 mm. The maximum adsorption capacity (N_0) increased with a decrease in particle size and initial ion concentration but increased with an increase in the bed height. The rate constant for Bohart–Adams model decreased with an increase in adsorbent size and initial concentration, and was higher at the bed height of 200 mm. The time required for 90% breakthrough decreased with increase in the flow rate, bed height, and initial ion concentration. The model results of the O&G breakthrough curve concentration have shown a fairly good agreement with experimental results. This analysis, considering the adsorbent's particle size, feed concentration, and bed heights indicated that the packed bed unit could be used for the treatment of O&G effluent to reduce the difficulties of oil refineries in Nigeria and other countries.

Keywords: Packed bed column, Adsorption, Oil and grease, Crude oil, Bohart–Adams kinetics, desalter effluent

1. INTRODUCTION

Crude oil is the first drilled from the petroleum reservoir alongside other reservoir fluids, such as gas and water, this crude oil is trapped near the top of the reservoir between the water below and gas above. Hence, the mixture of the reservoir fluids is separated into their components with the aid of a separator, thereafter crude oil being the most valuable fluid is sent to the crude oil refinery for refining. The separated crude oil sent to the refinery often contains water, inorganic salts, suspended solids, and water-soluble trace metals [1].

Usually, the first step in the crude oil refining is the pretreatment process which aims at subjecting the crude oil to the series of treatments to reduce the contaminants present to an acceptable standard, since the water in the crude oil makes the pipeline and the process of refining costly and unsteady, whereas the inorganic salts, such as sodium, magnesium, and calcium chlorides in the crude oil lead to corrosion, plugging and fouling of equipment used for refining. Crude oil pretreatment will also prevent the poisoning of catalysts present in the processing units. In other words, to remove all these contaminants, the following petroleum pretreatment processes are adopted: crude washing, crude heating, desulphurization, and pre-flashing. This study centers on the effluent wastewater as obtained from the crude washing units, also known as desalting and dewatering, as this unit is necessary for water and salt removal achieved by the combination of chemical and electrical systems, with the aid of a crude oil desalter. A crude oil desalter is schematically illustrated in **Fig. 1**.

The operation of a crude oil desalter comprises the following major steps: Separation by gravity settling, chemical injection, heating, adding of wash water (less water), mixing, and electrical coalescing [2]. The two most typical methods of crude oil desalting are chemical and electrostatic separation. In chemical desalting, the wash water and de-mulsifiers are added to the crude oil and then heated to enable the salts and other impurities dissolve into it or become attached to the wash water before it finally settles out. In electrostatic desalting, high voltage electrostatic charges are applied to the crude oil on suspended water globules in the bottom of the settling tank [1]. The process of desalting will produce effluent water that contains oil, grease, salts, mud, and other impurities.

The presence of oil and grease (O&G) in water bodies constitutes a major threat to the environment, most especially the aquatic life as the permissible level for O&G in a refinery effluent wastewater is 10 mg/L, as stated by the World Health Organization (WHO). However, the O&G levels in the desalter effluent range from 100-300 mg/L. This O&G may appear as a free oil, dispersed oil, emulsified oil, soluble oil, or as a coating or suspended matter [3]. These oily wastes discharge is responsible for the following harmful effects: (i) it may possess objectionable odors, (ii) it could cause undesirable appearance, (iii) it is highly flammable as it causes burn on the surface of the receiving water, thus leading to a potential safety hazard, and (iv) most importantly, it consumes dissolved oxygen necessary for the aquatic life survival and in greater quantities, it limits oxygen transfer [4, 5]; hence, this study seeks to solve this face-up through the help of an adsorption column.

Nowadays, there are lots of technologies or methods used for the treatment of O&G: they include coagulation, electro-coagulation, membrane distillation, adsorption, etc. [6]. Adsorption is a well-established and powerful technique for treating the domestic effluents containing organic or inorganic contaminants [7]. The choice of adsorption, as the treatment method in research, is due to its effective and economical nature in the use of various low-cost adsorbents, especially agricultural derived biomass [8, 9]. Modes of adsorption operation include: (i) *Batch flow system*: In the batch type of adsorption contact operation, the quantity of activated carbon is mixed continuously with a specific volume of wastewater until the pollutant in that solution has been decreased to the desired level [10]. The activated carbon is then removed and either discarded or regenerated for the use with another volume of solution. The batch-type processes are usually limited to the treatment of small volume of effluents; (ii) *Column flow system*: Column type continuous flow operation appears to have distinct advantages over the batch operation because rates of adsorption depend on the concentration of the solute in the solution being treated [11]. For the Column operation, the carbon is continuously in contact with a fresh solution; consequently, the concentration in the solution in contact with a given layer of carbon in a column is relatively constant. For continuous operation, the solid adsorbent may be added at the top of the column and spent adsorbent withdrawn from the bottom. Three types of continuous flow systems are usually encountered, namely the fixed bed adsorption system, the fluidized bed adsorption system, and the moving beds (or the expanded bed adsorption system).

This study aims to investigate the removal of O&G from refinery desalter effluent using adsorbent derived from rice husks in column adsorption method. The objectives of this study include: (i) to determine the characteristics of the prepared rice husks adsorbent (RHA) using both, the analytical and instrumental techniques, (ii) to evaluate the possibility of the chemically prepared activated rice husks in removing O&G from the refinery desalter effluent wastewater in a packed adsorption column, (iii) to access the effect of particle size, feed concentration and bed height on the breakthrough time in the packed column experiments, and (iv) to analyze the adsorption kinetic data generated, using a kinetic model, the Bohart-Adams model (based on an empirical relationship). This work provides for design data for O&G effluent management equipment.

This research study is essential to identify if the rice husks are good as an adsorbent by varying the optimum parameters or process variables on both, final concentration and breakthrough time. This adsorbent precursor, rice husks selected for this research are very accessible and affordable since they are obtained from agricultural biomass and also, they do not compete with human and animal survival since it is not a source of food.

Rice husks, also known as rice hulls, are the hard protective coverings of rice grains or seeds. They protect the seed during the growing season and they are formed from hard materials which include opaline silica and lignin. This husk is hard to eat or swallow, and is mostly indigestible to humans because of its enriched fiber components, hence it is an organic waste of rice milling and agro-based biomass industry usually produced in large quantity [12]. Rice husks can be used for producing adsorbents (activated carbons), beer brewing, fertilizer and substrate manufacture, insulation material, building material, and fuels for steam engines.

The data generated from the variation of process parameters in column adsorption process will prove very vital in the decision making, especially when there is a need to scale up to an industrial scale which in the long run will help in addressing societal/environmental needs,

reduce the unemployment situation in the country by the development of human capital and infrastructure.

Figure 1. Schematic of a crude oil desalter.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2. 1. Materials

The materials used for the laboratory work, including for the adsorbent (activated carbon) production and the adsorption experiments, were de-ionized water, distilled water, calcium chloride (CaCl₂, 99% purity), sodium chloride (NaCl), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), crude oil, and distilled water. The chemicals were used as-purchased, without additional purification.

2. 2. Collection and Preparation of Adsorbent Precursor (Rice Husks)

The rice husks (**Fig. 2**) were gathered from Abakaliki rice mill, Ebonyi state, Nigeria. It was then washed thoroughly with distilled water to remove dirt, and dried in the oven at 1050 °C for 6 h. Next, it was ground with a mortar and pestle, sieved to the desired particle size of 1-2 mm with a molecular sieve, and stored in an airtight container.

About 100 g of the rice husks were impregnated with 100 mL of the freshly prepared concentrated solution of NaOH (60%) with the impregnated ratio of 1:1. The sample was then heated in a water bath at 80 °C with the shaker at a speed of 150 rpm. Later it was dried in a memmert oven at 120 °C for 24 h. The impregnated rice husks were then carbonized at 500 °C under nitrogen gas flow for 3 h 30 min in a muffle furnace to produce charcoal. The resulting activated carbon was then cooled to room temperature, before being washed with distilled water several times to remove any remains of the NaOH until pH 6-7 was attained. Then, the washed sample was filtered with Whatman No. 1 filter paper and dried in an oven at 110 °C for 8 h.

The produced activated carbon was crushed and passed through different sieve sizes, and then stored in a tight bottle ready for use.

Figure 2. Rice husks

2. 3. Characterization of the Adsorbent

For the determination of the moisture content, thermal drying was adopted. 1.0 g of the dried activated carbons was weighed and placed in washed, dried, and weighed crucible. The crucibles were placed in an oven and dried at 105 °C to constant weight for 4 h [13]. The percentage of moisture content (%MC) was computed as follows:

$$\text{Moisture (\%)} = \frac{\text{loss in weight on drying (g)}}{\text{initial sample weight (g)}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The bulk density was determined by the method used by Devi *et al.* [14]. A sample of activated carbon was transferred into the aluminum plate and put into an oven to dry it to constant weight at a temperature of 105 °C for one hour. The weight of the empty density bottle of known volume was determined as 25 cm³ and the sample transfer into the bottle and the weight also recorded. The bulk density of the powder was calculated using:

$$\text{Bulk Density} = \frac{\text{weight of powder taken in bottle}}{25} \quad (2)$$

The porosity of the RHA was determined using Eq. (3):

$$\text{Porosity } (\eta) = \frac{V_v}{V_t} \quad (3)$$

where V_v = volume of void (cm³) = $V_t - V_s$; V_s = volume of solid (the adsorbent) used = $\frac{M_s}{G_s \rho_w}$
; V_t = total volume used for the experiment (cm³) = $\pi r^2 h$; r = radius of cylinder (cm); M_s =

mass of sample (g); h = height of cylinder (cm); G_s = specific gravity of sample; ρ_w = density of water (g/mL).

2 g of the activated carbon was weighed and transferred into a beaker. 20 mL of distilled water was measured and heated under reflux for 15 min [15]. The samples were allowed to stabilize before the pH was measured using a pH meter.

The standard test method for ash content-ASTM D2866-94 was used. A crucible was pre-heated in a muffle furnace to about 500 °C, cooled in a desiccator, and weighed. 1.0 g of activated carbon samples were transferred into the crucibles and re-weighed. The crucibles containing the samples were then placed in a cold muffle furnace and the temperature was allowed to rise to 500 °C. It was removed and allowed to cool in a desiccator to room temperature (30 °C) and re-weighed again. The ash content was calculated using Eq. (4):

$$\text{Ash}(\%) = \frac{\text{Ash weight (g)}}{\text{Oven dry weight (g)}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

The Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) analysis was used to determine the functional groups present in the activated carbons produced from the rice husk and corn cob, as used for the column adsorption. This analysis was done using the FTIR Shimadzu 8400S spectrophotometer (**Fig. 3**), with samples prepared by the conventional KBr disc method.

Figure 3. FTIR Shimadzu 8400S spectrophotometer

2. 4. Preparation of the Adsorbate (Simulated Desalter Effluent)

1000 mL of deionized water was measured into a 1000 mL beaker. Thereafter, 50 g of NaCl (**Fig. 4a**) and 5 g of CaCl (**Fig. 4b**) were measured with the aid of an electric weighing balance and then poured into a 1000 mL volumetric flask. After this, the deionized water was gradually poured into the flask and mixed until the 1000 mL mark was reached.

400 mL of the brine solution was measured out and poured back into the 1000 mL beaker. Thereafter, 300 mg/L of crude oil (**Fig. 5a**) was injected into the 400 mL brine solution with the aid of a syringe. The mixture was then agitated using the magnetic stirrer at 15,000 rpm for 15 min. The left behind 600 mL brine solution was then added and stirred at a reduced speed of 11,000 rpm for an extra 5 min.

Then, the simulated desalter effluent (**Fig. 5b**) was poured into a collection bottle (effluent bottle). This process was repeated for other concentrations of the feed (200 and 400 mg/L). The total time for the preparation of effluent was around the range of 45 min to 1 h.

Figure 4. (a) NaCl pellets, (b) CaCl pellets

Figure 5. (a) Crude oil sample, (b) Simulated desalter effluent

2.5. Column Sorption Experiment

The sorption of O&G on RHA was studied with the use of a packed adsorption column of 10 mm internal diameter and 600 mm length, which was packed with activated carbon of changing heights (100, 200, and 300 mm) having a mesh at the bottom of the column (**Fig. 6b**). The containing vessel, having the effluent feed was kept at a high elevation and a peristaltic

pump (**Fig. 6a**) was operated to send the feed into the adsorption column, set up at a constant flow rate of 10.5 mL/min.

The total adsorption time was 60 min and the effluent samples were taken at an interval of 5 min. The feed concentration was varied (200, 300, and 400 mg/L) as well as the particle sizes of each of the RHA (150, 300, and 600 μm). Effluent samples collected, were tested for absorbance through the UV-visible spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 980 nm. Influence of the most important parameters, the feed concentration, bed height, and the adsorbent particle size on the breakthrough curves and adsorption performance were studied. A breakthrough curve in adsorption is the course of the effluent adsorptive concentration at the outlet of a fixed bed adsorber [16]. The breakthrough curve is plotted using the ratio of effluent and feed (influent) concentrations (C_t/C_0) against time for changing operating.

Figure 6. (a) Peristaltic pump, (b) Column adsorption setup

2. 6. Modeling of Column Study Results

The study of sorption kinetics in the management of wastewater is important since it provides valuable insights into the reaction pathways and mechanism of the adsorption process [17, 18]. To examine the mechanism of the adsorption process, an appropriate model of kinetics is needed to analyze the rate data [17].

The Bohart-Adams model was chosen to calculate the performance of the adsorption column. The Bohart-Adams model is extensively applied for designing a fixed-bed column; it is based on surface reaction theory [19]. The adsorption rate is in linear relation with the fraction of adsorption capacity that remains on the surface of the adsorbent.

The mathematical relationship can be given as [19, 20]:

$$\ln\left(\frac{C_t}{C_0}\right) = K_{AB}C_0t - K_{AB}N_0\left(\frac{z}{U_0}\right) \quad (5)$$

where, C_o = influent concentrations (mg/L), C_t = effluent concentrations (mg/L), K_{AB} = kinetic constant (L/mg min), N_o = saturation concentration (mg/L), t = flow time (min), z = bed depth of the fixed bed column (cm), and U_o = superficial velocity (cm/min).

A plot of $\ln(C_t/C_o)$ versus t gives the value of correlation coefficients (R^2), kinetic constant (K_{AB}), and saturation concentration (N_o).

Figure 7. Schematic representation of the packed adsorption experiment

3. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Effect of adsorbent size on final concentration and breakthrough curve

The influence of adsorbent size (150, 300, 600 μm) on effluent concentration and per cent removal was studied at a constant flow rate of 10.5 mL/min, the concentration of 300 mg/L, and bed height of 300 mm at several intervals (**Table 1** and **Fig. 8a**). 150 μm particle size was the optimum size; it took lengthier time to attain saturation time than it took 300 and 600 μm particle size, hence it can be proposed for scale-up purposes, whereas, for laboratory-scale, 300 μm was selected, because 150 μm shifted the adsorption column from being a fixed bed to a

fluidized bed. Hence, there was a need for more control to maintain the fixed bed adsorption column at 150 μm .

Table 1. The effect of particle size on effluent concentration (C_e)

600 μm	300 μm	150 μm	Time
161.4	94.68	57.39	5 min
162.57	95.58	58.86	10 min
163.17	97.02	59.13	20 min
163.32	98.19	59.43	40 min
163.98	98.64	59.58	60 min
164.19	98.79	61.32	90 min
164.4	99.36	62.07	120 min
166.95	108.81	62.34	150 min
179.97	118.08	62.34	180 min
189.72	121.23	62.34	210 min
208.14	130.98	64.11	240 min
223.2	142.08	74.46	300 min
238.68	153.96	82.71	330 min
246.87	170.31	90.06	360 min
259.32	178.02	103.02	390 min
270	191.46	108.69	420 min
282.99	206.64	120.36	450 min
296.31	217.05	138	480 min
299.43	243.66	147.33	510 min
300	262.32	176.34	540 min
300	275.61	195.06	570 min
300	299.46	213.09	600 min
300	300	231.27	630 min
300	300	249.45	660 min
300	300	267.66	690 min
300	300	285.84	720 min
300	300	297.27	750 min
300	300	300	780 min

Figure 8. Influence of adsorbent particle size on (a) the %removal and (b) the breakthrough curve for the RHA

The effect of particle size on the breakthrough curve at a flow rate of 10.5 mL/min, bed height of 300 mm, and feed concentration of 300 mg/L, is revealed in Fig. 8b. It was observed that the particle size increased from 150, 300, and 600 μm when the breakpoint time decreased from 665, 530, and 390 min. This was carried out at a breakthrough concentration of 90%.

3. 2. Effect of Bed Height on the Final Concentration and Breakthrough Curve

At a constant flow rate of 10.5 mL/min, the concentration of 300 mg/L, and particle size of 300 μm , it was observed from Table 2 and Fig. 9a that 300 mm bed height needed a lengthier time to reach saturation when compared to the bed heights of 100 and 200 mm. This is due to the availability of higher sorption sites with the bed height [21]. In other words, the higher bed height corresponds to a higher amount of the absorbed O&G [17].

The influence of the inlet adsorbate concentration on the breakthrough curves at a constant concentration of 300 mg/L, the particle size of 300 μm , and a flow rate of 10.5 mL/min is presented in Fig. 9b. It was observed that, as the bed height rises from 100, 200, and 300 mm, the breakthrough time increased from 390, 480, to 700 min. This was done using a breakthrough concentration of 60% for RHA.

Therefore, the experiment on the effect of bed height shows a diminution in the minimum effluent concentration, with the bed height keeping other parameters stable. A minimum effluent concentration is the average concentration of the O&G at the column outlet in the initial constant phase.

Table 2. Effect of bed height on concentration (C_e)

300 mm	200 mm	100 mm	Time
7.89	61.23	112.26	5 min
12.87	61.35	118.86	10 min
14.61	62.1	119.13	20 min
16.08	62.97	122.34	40 min
17.52	63.69	129.81	60 min
20.535	64.23	132.054	90 min
22.782	64.884	135.912	120 min
25.029	65.538	139.77	150 min
27.276	66.192	143.628	180 min
29.523	66.846	147.486	210 min
31.77	67.5	151.344	240 min
34.017	68.154	155.202	300 min
36.264	68.808	159.06	330 min
38.511	69.462	162.918	360 min
40.758	70.116	166.776	390 min
43.005	70.77	170.634	420 min
45.252	71.424	174.492	450 min
47.499	72.078	178.35	480 min
49.746	72.732	182.208	510 min
51.993	73.386	186.066	540 min
54.24	74.04	189.924	570 min
56.487	74.694	193.782	600 min
58.734	75.348	197.64	630 min
60.981	76.002	201.498	660 min
63.228	76.656	205.356	690 min
65.475	77.31	209.214	720 min

Figure 9. Effect of the bed height on (a) %removal, and (b) the breakthrough curve for the RHA

3. 3. Effect of Feed Concentration on the Effluent Concentration and Breakthrough Curve

Table 3. Effect of feed concentration on effluent concentration (C_e)

400 mg/L	300 mg/L	200 mg/L	Time
238.12	96.51	38.26	5 min
248.24	97.68	39.24	10 min
255.24	99	39.42	20 min
257.36	99.15	39.62	40 min
260.88	100.89	39.72	60 min
265.36	105.15	40.88	90 min
270.6	105.57	41.38	120 min
270.8	106.17	41.56	150 min
273.16	107.04	41.56	180 min
276.08	110.25	41.56	210 min
289.44	113.01	42.74	240 min
300.8	116.1	49.12	300 min
317.52	119.07	55.72	330 min
333.88	134.07	58.5	360 min
358.24	149.07	62.22	390 min
377.28	158.07	73.92	420 min
396.64	179.04	79.64	450 min
400	194.04	92.76	480 min
400	218.04	104.46	510 min
400	245.04	116.18	540 min
400	270.03	125.88	570 min
400	286.53	139.6	600 min
400	294.6	151.3	630 min
400	297.99	162.66	660 min
400	300	177.82	690 min
400	300	186.2	720 min

At a constant flow rate of 10.5 mL/min, the concentration of 300 mg/L and bed height of 300 mm, it was noticed (**Table 3**, and **Fig. 10a**) that the higher the concentration of the adsorbate, the shorter the time of saturation of the bed. At higher concentrations, the accessibility of O&G particles for the adsorption is higher, which led to a better elimination of the O&G.

The effect of inlet adsorbate concentration on the breakthrough curve at the bed height of 300 mm and a flow rate of 10.5 mL/min is shown in Fig. **10b**. It was seen that the inlet concentration increases from 200, 300, to 400 mg/L. The breakthrough time decreases from 568 to 475, to 210 min for rice husks.

On increasing the inlet concentration, the breakthrough curve became steeper, and breakthrough volume decreased because of the lower mass transfer flux from the bulk solution to the particle surface, due to the weaker driving force [21]. This was done with a breakthrough concentration of 70% for RHA.

Figure 10. Effect of feed concentration on (a) %removal, and (b) the breakthrough curve for the RHA

3. 4. Bohart-Adams Model for the Column Kinetic Study

This Bohart-Adams model was suited to the investigational data for the explanation of the initial portion of the breakthrough curve [19]. This method is based on the estimation of the representative factors, maximum adsorption capacity (N_o) and the mass transfer coefficient (K_{AB}) from the straight-line plot of $\ln(C_e/C_o)$ against time t at different particle sizes, bed height, and feed concentration, as plotted shown in **Fig. 11**.

The mass transfer coefficient, that is kinetic constant and saturation concentration (K_{AB} and N_o) values were calculated from the slope and intercept of linear curves, respectively, and

detailed in **Table 4**. From the Table it was seen, that the K_{AB} increases with an increase in the bed height. K_{AB} decreases due to the decrease in the existing active sorption sites with decreases in the particle size, which is higher with the small particles. Therefore, at 150, 300, and 600 μm , the kinetic constants are 500, 367, and 200 mL/min , respectively.

Figure 11. Bohart-Adams kinetic plot for the column adsorption on adsorbent: Effect of adsorbent particle siz.

Table 4. Bohart-Adams parameters for O&G adsorption on RHA

Kinetic parameters	Particle size (μm)			Initial feed concentration (mg/L)			Bed height (mm)		
	150	300	600	200	300	400	100	200	300
K_{AB} ($\text{L}/\text{mg}\cdot\text{min}$) $\times 10^{-4}$	240.60	181.67	101.33	371.50	183.67	62.00	77.33	31.00	3.10
N_0 (mg/L)	3782.13	3305.64	3070.99	1363.33	887.40	1238.96	5513.40	22943.81	487794.89
R^2	0.9339	0.9598	0.8923	0.9409	0.9299	0.9100	0.9906	0.9984	0.8586

Figure 12. Bohart-Adams plot for the column adsorption on RHA: Effect of feed concentration

Figure 13. Bohart-Adams kinetic plot for the column adsorption on RHA: Effect of bed height

As the particle size rose, the capacity of adsorption dropped, as evidently outlined in **Fig. 12**. At 150 μm , the N_0 is 76780.048 mg/L, and at 600 μm , the N_0 is 64518.053 mg/L. The regression coefficients (R^2) show a high level of accuracy of the linear equations obtained, so

the equations can be employed to forecast any desired values. The kinetic constant increases with increasing the bed height. At particle size of 150 μm , K_{AB} is 500×10^{-6} (L/mg·min).

3. 5. Characterization Results of the RHA

3. 5. 1. Physicochemical properties of the RHA

Physicochemical properties describe the usability of an adsorbent for a sorption process. Physicochemical properties obtained for the RHA are presented in **Table 5**.

Bulk density is an important parameter of powdered solids. Bulk density specifies the fiber content of the precursor [22]. The American Water Work Association (AWWA) has set a lower limit on the bulk density at 0.25 g/mL for activated carbon to be of practical use [14, 23]. The bulk density values of the prepared adsorbent (Table 5) satisfies this condition.

The porosity of the RHA adsorbent is an important physicochemical property, and it was obtained by the first determining of the total volume of the cylinder used for the experiment and also determining the volume of solid. The value obtained was 0.231.

The pH value of the RHA was found to be 7.1 ± 0.28 . This is in agreement with Idris *et al.* [24] that the activated carbons produced from precursors with a low ash content have been found to have low pH. The pHs near neutral are helpful for the treatment of all cases of dye wastewater and the carbons can also be used for drinking water purification [22, 23].

Volatile matter is due to the presence of organic compounds present. The activated carbon with the lowest percentage of fixed carbon will have the lowest adsorption capacity [25]. From the result obtained it can be seen that the activated carbon has a good percentage of fixed carbon.

Table 5. Physicochemical properties of the RHA.

Properties	Unit	Value
Moisture content	%	5.5
Bulk density	g/mL	0.214
Porosity	-	0.296
pH	-	7.1 ± 0.28
Ash content	%	37

3. 5. 2. FTIR Study of the RHA

The FTIR analysis was used to examine the surface functional groups of the adsorbents and to identify those groups responsible for oil and adsorption. Adsorption in the IR region takes place because of the rotational and vibrational movements of the molecular groups and chemical band of a molecule [23, 26]. The FTIR spectra of the RHA is shown in **Table 6** and **Fig. 14**. The FTIR analysis of the carbon indicates the presence of alkanes, alkenes, nitro compounds, alcohols, carboxylic acids, aromatics, and phenols. The O-H stretch in alcohols which is very strong and broadband; this band is vital in sorption sites.

Table 6. The FTIR analysis of the RHA.

S/N	Peaks (cm ⁻¹)	Functional group	Remark
1	704.0, 851.3	=C–H bend in alkenes	strong
2	1077.2, 1148.0, 1244.9	C–O in carboxylic acid	strong
3	1338.1	N–O symmetric stretch in nitro compounds	medium
4	1420.1	C–C stretch (in–ring) in aromatics	medium
5	1520.8	N–O asymmetric stretch in nitro compound	strong
6	1640.0	C=C stretching in alkenes	medium
7	1707.1	C=O stretch carboxylic acids	strong
8	2855.1, 2926.8	C–H stretch in alkanes	medium
9	3272.9	O–H stretch, H–bonded in alcohols and phenols	strong

Figure 14. FTIR spectrum of the RHA

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to investigate the removal of O&G from refinery desalter effluent using activated carbon derived from rice husk in a packed bed column adsorption. Characterization

of the rice husks derived activated carbon showed, that it is a good raw material for the production of activated carbon, as their physicochemical properties satisfy the set standards. The effect of various parameters, such as particle size, feed concentration, and bed height on breakthrough time was investigated in the packed column experiments and the data generated from the column studies were modeled using the empirical relationship based on the Bohart-Adams model, as it analyzed the adsorption kinetics. The Kinetic constant (K_{AB}) of 500×10^{-6} (L/mg·min) was obtained at a particle size of 150 μm . More agricultural biomass wastes can be used to produce activated carbon with their physicochemical properties analyzed and compared to select the best performing adsorbent. Also other models, such as the Nelson and Yoon model, Thomas models, etc. can be used to study the kinetics of the O&G removal with their various kinetic constants determined and compared.

Acknowledgement

This research is an undergraduate thesis submitted to the Department of Chemical Engineering, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria, supervised by Engr. Dr. Mrs. Chinenye A. Igwegbe and Engr. C. J. Umembamalu. The authors wish to acknowledge Prof. J.T. Nwabanne for providing the required equipment and inspiration for this research.

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